

STUDY OF THE INFLUENCE OF THE PHYTOPATHOGENIC FUNGUS FUSARIUM OXYSPORUM ON THE BIOCHEMICAL PROCESSES OF LOCAL SOY VARIETIES

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Annotation: this article will talk about the study of the soybean plant and the influence of various fungi on it among the leguminous grain crops that are being planted in our country

Keywords: soy, fusarium, oxysporum, phytopathogen, fungi, legumes, protein, soil fertility:

Fusarium oxysporum is an important pathogen that reduces the yield of soybeans, which causes seedling diseases and root rot. In 2007, a study on this disease took place in Iowa. This study shows the pH and temperature of Fusarium fungus. Root rot caused by Fusarium graminearum in the shade is more common when grown in sand than in sand, and is more common in soils with a pH of 6 than a pH of 8. The absorbed form of nitrogen showed increased tomato root rot. However, the storage temperature of sweet potatoes (13-15 ° C) is Fusarium spp. not suitable for growing conditions (25-30 ° c). Hence the root rot caused by Fusarium spp. during long storage periods in residual soil, slow Fusarium further studies are required to determine the time of infection by the spp. However, it should be noted that filamentous fungi do not always produce toxins. The toxin production of these fungi is strongly dependent on environmental conditions such as weather conditions. High water activity and a temperature of about 28-30 ° C are mainly b this promotes the growth and toxin production of fungi observed at 25⁰c likewise, the most favorable temperature range for the growth and sporulation of Fusarium oxysporum was between 25 and 30 ° C. Another study found that temperatures of 22 0 c or higher were the most suitable for Fusarium oxysporum. However, soy cultivation is threatened by various pathogens.

Among the most economically important are fungi belonging to the complex of *Fusarium solani* species, which are responsible for the syndrome of sudden death of the shadow, and a complex of *Fusarium oxysporum* species, in which shade root rot leads to Burns of seedlings. In its synthetic environment, sclerotia is poorly developed at neutral or alkaline pH. Lowering the pH of the soil from 8.0 to 6.0 Root by influencing the interaction between pathogens and their antagonists eliminated the effect on decay diseases. For all analyzes, the isolates were grown in the LB environment for 48 hours at 28 * C and diluted to 0.13 optical density (OD 600Nm). *Fusarium* synthetic potato dextrose was grown in the agar (PDA) environment and incubated at 28 • C for 7 days. By species, FW's disease severity showed the greatest difference in *Fusarium Sol* resistance and sensitivity phenotypes at temperatures below 25 ° C. The distribution of plant pathogens in the soil depends on many environmental factors such as temperature, relative humidity, pH level and the size of the soil particles. In 2015 and 2016, a study was also carried out in which radish seedlings, consisting of 225 inclusions, were vaccinated in the same way in a greenhouse from 26 ° C to 29 ° C with natural light. Let's say in place of the conclusion in this research work, I have gained in-depth knowledge about the study and fight against various fungal diseases found in soy varieties, how to treat a plant from this disease.

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